

**THE KORBOSHIES OF TURKESTAN - THEY ARE NOT PUBLISHERS:
FREEDOM FIGHTERS**

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Abstract This article discusses the consequences of Turkestan becoming a colonial state, the emergence of national liberation movements and their main reasons, the emergence of the terms "Korboshi" and "printing", the essence and results of the movement.

Key words: Bolshevik, General-governorship, warlord, printing movement, atheism, socialist activities

In the 40s-60s of the 19th century, after the 4th stage of the colonization of Turkestan by Tsarist Russia, the Kokan, Khiva Khanates and the Bukhara Emirate, located in this region and having a great history of several centuries, gradually it was slowly ended as an independent and colonial state. The inhabitants of these countries (Uzbek, Tajik, Kazakh, Karakalpak, Turkmen, Kyrgyz peoples, etc.) were forced to completely forget their identity, history and traditions.

In 1867, the General Governorate of Turkestan was established in our country, and in Petersburg, which is the capital, currents supporting different views emerged and tried to seize the power of the state, and as a result, there were several changes of power. Regardless of which movement came to power, they all had the same goal, that is, to further increase their colonial policy and oppression in the region of Central Asia, which is a deposit of natural resources. The initial movement of independence against the Soviet regime under the rule of the Bolsheviks, one of such movements in the Turkestan region, began in the last ten days of February 1918 in the vicinity of Kokan. The first group of counter-movements is associated

with the names of such leaders as Kichik Ergash (1885-1918) and Katta Ergash (1882-1921), who were born in the village of Bachkir near Kokan.¹

The term Qorboshi was originally used in the Middle Ages as the official of the armory (kor) of the Central Asian khanates and the head of the armory, various weapons and cannon manufacturing enterprises, that is, the storehouses. became the head of the local police in the period before the "October" coup in Turkestan and later became the title of the leaders of the independence movement against the Soviet regime in Turkestan.

In the Fergana valley, by the middle of 1918, about 100 soldiers and their groups fought valiantly against the units of the Red Army. However, the essence and actions of the national liberation movement were falsified in the official documents of the Soviet authorities, and it was misinterpreted as a "printing" movement, and its participants, i.e., the guards and their supporters, as "printers". The main reason for the emergence of national liberation movements in Turkestan was the colonialism and chauvinist policy of the Soviet government in the country.

The initial socialist measures carried out by the Bolsheviks (transfer of enterprises to the state, abolition of private property and grain monopoly, restriction of Islam, propaganda of atheism, closure of mosques, private schools and courts, introduction of forced and hard labor , the closing of markets, etc.) and the looting and raids of the Red Army fighters gave special intensity and scope to the independence movement, which led to the development of this movement, which became more and more popular. The real essence and purpose of the Korboshi movement was to fight for the national perspective and independence of Turkestan. Despite the fact that the movement sometimes increased and decreased, the composition of groups changed, secondary goals changed, it did not stop moving

¹—History of Uzbekistan: textbook for students of the 10th grade of secondary educational institutions and secondary special, vocational educational institutions / Author: Q.Rajabov, A.Zamonov. 1st edition. T.: Publishing house named after Gafur Ghulam, 2017. 144 p.

towards its goal, and the true essence of this movement remained the struggle for the independence of Turkestan.

The composition of the groups led by the leaders were peasants, peasants, workers, artisans and intellectuals who could not stand silently by the oppression of the Soviet authorities. Fighters from different strata of the population were the main driving force of the independence movement. Religious leaders and wealthy people supported the movement of armed resistance to the Soviet regime both morally and economically. Mulla Khaliqul from Samarkand: "Khoja Eshankul the Elder, Khoja Shodibek, Rajabbek, Abduraufboy, Ikromboy, Mulla Odil, Ne'matullabek and others, who were the owners of the region, were given 200 pieces of gold, 200 pieces of gold of 5 soums for the fight against the enemy. I urge you to collect coins, 50 boots, 200 arshins of gazlama and other assets. All these efforts are made for the independence of the Motherland. No one lives forever in this bright world... Fight until your last blood!" calls the people to action. A number of influential religious leaders and wealthy people also put their signatures on this call letter.

The essence of the movement and the courage of the people fighting for independence were also recognized by the representatives of the Soviet commander. One of them, M.Frunze, the commander of the Turkestan Front, wrote in his letter to the Center: "Fighting against tyranny means fighting against a completely new, unique enemy." The main structure of the independence movement was formed by the local population, that is, the Uzbek, Kazakh, Karakalpak, Turkmen, and Kyrgyz peoples. Despite the large number of Uzbeks, there were representatives of European nationalities, even Russians, in the ranks of the movement, who fought alongside the local population against the Soviet regime. The role and service of the warlords in organizing the people's movement, which was aroused to struggle, was great. From the first years of the movement, there were about 30,000 soldiers under the command of Madaminbek, 20,000 under Shermuhammadbek, and 8,000 under Katta Ergash. The Korboshis were the

military leaders of the independence fighters, who were famous among the people for their combativeness. At one time, Kichik Ergash, Katta Ergash, Madaminbek, Shermuhammadbek, Islam Polvan in the Fergana Valley; Ochilbek, Bahrombek and others led the movement in Samarkand region. Most of them were literate and intelligent people. Uzbek female fighters such as Shakarkhan, Muhyiddinbek's mother, and Nadira Kyz are among the people who left a glorious mark on the history of the national independence struggle in Turkestan.

Despite the fact that being associated with the pro-independence movement and its leaders, participating in mass demonstrations was punishable by imprisonment, exile or death, large-scale repression and the intensification of military operations by the Red Army did not deter the pro-independence people from fighting. Ibrohimbek, a field commander, went down in Soviet history as the most famous leader of the "printers' movement". He was one of the independence fighters who waged an armed struggle against the Soviet government in the 1930s. Korboshi, who fought against the Soviet government for many years, knew in advance what would happen to him, but he did not turn back from his chosen path. Ibrahimbek, the representative of the leadership, was arrested and sentenced to death by the court. It was only after 90 years that Ibrahimbek's name was vindicated and it was recognized that he was not a "printer" but a freedom fighter. There are several thousands of freedom fighters condemned as "repressors" and sentenced to severe punishments. How many fighters are not mentioned in historical documents? If the independence movement in our country had been small-scale, the authoritarian regime would not have organized hundreds of mobilizations against this movement.

This people's movement left an indelible tragic mark on the lives and fate of millions of our compatriots. According to some confirmed official data, it cost the dear lives of more than a million local people. It caused thousands of families to leave their homeland and go to foreign lands. Moreover, because of this national tragedy, countless people were exiled and exiled to remote areas of the former

Soviet Union. After all, the great efforts made by our great-grandfathers, condemned as "printers", when our mother Uzbekistan turned towards independence and became Musharraf to the good times, and the people of today's happy generation can fully enjoy the supreme blessing of independence, are full of There is no small example of the sacrifices that have been made. Their bright, shining memory should always be kept in the minds and consciousness of the people of the present generation, and should be remembered with a sense of pride.

List of used literature:

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